

WATS 5350: CAPSTONE II

SUMMIT CREEK, UT

LOW TECH PROCESS BASED RESTORATION

MANAGEMENT AND RESTORATION OF AQUATIC ECOSYSTEMS

Photo: Summit Creek flowing over the road after Spring 2023 floods.

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Executive Summary

This restoration project on Summit Creek in Smithfield Canyon, UT, spanning a 1.3-mile stretch, aims to combat ecological degradation resulting from human activities like grazing and road development. A collaborative effort between the Forest Service, Utah Division of Wildlife Resources, and local communities, the project employs low-tech, process-based restoration methods to bolster stream complexity, enhance floodplain connectivity, and elevate habitat quality. Beginning with a comprehensive planning phase, the project undertakes an adaptive management framework, assessing problems, structural starvation, and the appropriateness of interventions. Design strategies revolve around creating complexes of structures to mimic natural processes, aiming to reactivate abandoned side channels, increase hydraulic variability, and widen the channel for improved habitat quality. Phase 1 implementation involves constructing structures to achieve immediate restoration goals, with subsequent phases planned to address remaining objectives and ensure long-term recovery. The project's as-built phase 1 involves the construction of structures to achieve immediate restoration goals, laying the groundwork for subsequent phases to further enhance ecological resilience and habitat quality on Summit Creek. Our complexes built on April 13, 2024, were successful in achieving our overarching goal. Ultimately, the project endeavors to restore Summit Creek's ecological functionality, mitigate flood and drought risks, and support the recovery of native aquatic and riparian species, thereby fostering the resilience of the aquatic ecosystem in the region.

Introduction

Project Background

Summit Creek is an 8km tributary to the Bear River situated in Smithfield Canyon, Utah, USA, and at its mouth, drains approximately 25 square miles and on average, flows at 38 cubic feet per second (cfs). Northern Utah typically experiences cold winters with average temperatures ranging from 20°F to 35°F (-6°C to 2°C) and hot summers with potential temperatures reaching extremes of -10°F to -20°F (-23°C to -29°C) in winter and 100°F to 110°F (38°C to 43°C) or higher in summer. This leads to a typical hydrological cycle dominated by snowfall during winter and subsequent melt in spring/summer. A large portion of snowmelt infiltrates and re-emerges as surface water through springs. Our project will focus on ~1.3 miles of Summit Creek starting at the Smithfield Canyon Road bridge just below Smithfield Campground, moving up to the base of Indian Canyon, a spur canyon within Smithfield Canyon. This section of Summit Creek has endured the impacts of diverse land uses such as grazing and road development, leading to compromised ecological functionality and reductions in habitat quality. The alteration of natural processes has resulted in floodplain disconnection, and reduced riparian vegetation, and a general paucity of in-stream habitat complexity. To address these challenges, the implementation of low-tech, process-based restoration methods, holds significant promise. With low tech interventions, we aim to increase stream complexity, which promotes riverine processes for greater ecological resilience. These interventions aid in restoring the stream's geomorphological balance, mitigating flood and drought risk, and improving habitats to support the recovery of native aquatic and riparian species.

Problem(s)

The entirety of stream length in our project area has anthropogenically imposed confining margins, with a dirt road on the river's right. The stream has steep banks with its floodplains typically sitting about 2 - 4 feet above the water surface level. The overstory of the riparian area is mostly dominated by encroaching upland trees.

Description of Restoration Project

The project is an implementation of low-tech, process based restoration techniques to address issues of floodplain connectivity, and general ecological degradation along Summit Creek.

Broad Management Goals

The management goals for this project are to maintain a recreational trout fishery, and recreational activities like camping and trail use, and promote general conservation efforts. These objectives are set collaboratively by the Forest Service and the Utah Division of Wildlife Resources, with shared interests in sustainable resource management and conservation/restoration.

Specific Project Goals

The specific project goals are to enhance a recreational trout fishery (and potentially bolster a restored a native cutthroat fishery) through habitat restoration utilizing low-tech Process Based Restoration (PBR) methods. These objectives are derived from the directives of the United States Forest Service (USFS) and the Utah Division of Wildlife Resources (UDWR), the clients overseeing the project.

Project Location

Summit Creek Watershed and Restoration Area

Figure 1: Map displaying watershed area, and upper/lower extent of project, and the watersheds location in Northern Utah.

The entire project area lies within the Uinta-Wasatch-Cache National Forest and is managed by the US Forest Service. The project will involve collaboration with downstream private landowners that may be impacted, as well as coordination with the Utah Division of Wildlife Resources. The project encompasses a ~1.3 mile section of Summit Creek in Smithfield Canyon. The limits are defined by the confining valley-bottom margins as well imposed anthropogenic boundaries including a campground and multi-use road. The project extends to the valley bottom on both sides of the creek, involving riparian zones within the floodplain.

The Summit Creek restoration project involves:

- Site Assessment: Conduct a detailed assessment of the Summit Creek area including topography, soil composition, vegetation, and existing flow and sediment flux patterns.
- Stakeholder Engagement: Collaborate with local communities, private landowners, and governmental agencies to gain support and ensure the success of the restoration efforts.
- Instream Structure Construction: Implement the construction of low tech structures strategically along Summit Creek to diversify hydraulic variation. This includes selecting appropriate locations that minimize impact to the road and campground, designing structures, and executing construction activities.
- Monitoring and Evaluation: Establish a monitoring system to assess the effectiveness of interventions, track changes in water flow, sediment deposition, and observe ecological shifts over time.
- Project Documentation: Prepare detailed documentation of the restoration process, including construction methodologies, and any unforeseen challenges faced during the project.
- Environmental Compliance: Ensure compliance with environmental regulations and obtain necessary permits for construction activities within the project area.

Planning & Design Methods

Planning for low-tech process-based restoration is similar to planning for other forms of restoration. We adapt the Conservation Planning Process to show what aspects of the process are distinctive to low-tech process-based restoration. The Conservation Planning Process follows an adaptive management framework and has three phases: i) a Collection and Analysis (focused on planning), ii) a Decision Support (focused on design), and iii) an Application and Evaluation (focused on implementation). For low-tech restoration, we pose four screening questions to identify where and if low-tech process-based restoration is appropriate. In the Collection and Analysis Phase, current conditions of the riverscape (valley bottom), constraints and recovery potential are identified to help frame appropriate and realistic treatments and objectives in the design. Low-tech restoration to reverse structural starvation of riverscapes frequently takes more than one treatment (and design). Therefore, in the design phase we set expectations for how many treatments might be necessary to achieve the long-term restoration goal of a self-sustaining riverscape. The implementation of a design involves an iteration between carrying out an individual treatment of structural additions and evaluation. Ultimately, it is assumed project goals will be met if the processes of wood accumulation and/or beaver dam activity make the transition from being mimicked and promoted by treatments to occurring on their own in a self-sustaining fashion. As such, the need for additional treatments versus recognizing the project has achieved its goals is evaluated with respect to the sustainability of these processes.

Design

A complex is a group of structures designed to work together to mimic and/or promote specific processes to achieve one or more project objectives. Complexes are the building blocks of a low-tech restoration design. The low-tech restoration design process for complexes: is rapid, low-cost, flexible, transparent, field-based, and generates clear and

testable design hypotheses; hypothesizes the hydraulic zone of influence (laterally constrained by the valley bottom) of the treatment, which helps set expectations for the extent of impact of the treatment relative to overall project goals and reach objectives for recovery potential; identifies low-flow, typical-flood, and extreme-flood hypotheses (i.e., process-based responses), which articulate the connection between the processes initially mimicked, later promoted, and hopefully eventually taken over naturally by the system. Design of low-tech restoration projects focuses on the complex-scale rather than the individual structure to maintain focus on the scope of riverscape degradation due to structural starvation.

Planning Process

This project follows an adaptive management framework and has three phases: i) a Collection and Analysis (focused on planning), ii) a Decision Support (focused on design), and iii) an Application and Evaluation (focused on implementation). First, we identify problems and opportunities for restoration based on broad management goals and specific project goals for Summit Creek. Next, we pose and answer screening questions to identify where and if low-tech process-based restoration is appropriate. In the Collection and Analysis Phase, current conditions of the riverscape (valley bottom), constraints (i.e., risks, including a risk vs. opportunity assessment) and recovery potential are identified to help frame appropriate and realistic treatments and objectives in the design. Low-tech restoration to reverse structural starvation of riverscapes frequently takes more than one treatment (and design). Therefore, in the design phase we set expectations for how many treatments might be necessary to achieve the long-term restoration goal of a self-sustaining riverscape.

Problems & Opportunities

The problem that this restoration project aims to address primarily stems from structural starvation of the riverscape. As Summit Creek is flanked by a dirt road on the river's right almost for the entirety of the project site and has steep banks with its floodplains typically sitting about 2 - 4 feet above the water surface level, the stream has developed a simple morphology which is lacking in high quality fish habitat. The overstory of the riparian area is also mostly dominated by encroaching upland trees. Opportunities for restoration are abundant, and low-tech approaches offer cost-effective and scalable solutions, aligning with the goal of long-term recovery of historic geomorphic and habitat conditions (i.e., anastomosing; Figure 4). Summit Creek is currently in the widening (stage 4) phase, and partial recovery (constraints imposed by existing infrastructure prevent full recovery) of the anastomosing (stage 0) phase is the principal goal of this project.

Assessment of Structural Starvation and Appropriateness of Low-Tech

A field visit has shown that there is an extremely low degree of hydraulic complexity forcing structure in the stream. Three structures were counted in the ~1.3 miles of stream within the project reach, and only two diffluences and confluences were counted along the same reach. This low degree of in-stream structure paired with the accessibility and wade-ability of Summit Creek make it a highly appropriate site to implement LTPBR solutions.

INDICATOR	EXISTING	Phase 1 Goal	Phase 2 Goal	Phase 3 Goal
Proportion active channel(s) & floodplain (by VB area)	~10%	~ 25%	~ 40%	~ 90% ± 10
Number of active channels (i.e. braiding index)	1.1	1.5	2 - 3	3 - 5
LWD accumulations (structures per mile)	~ 1-2 /mi	~50 ± 10 /mi (PALS)	~100 ± 10/mi (PALS) (Add 100 more PALS & some natural)	~ 100 ± 50/mi (natural wood accumulations & wood accumulations on PALS indistinguishable)
Beaver dam density (dams per mile)	0/mi	50 ± 10 /mi (BDAs)	75 ± 20 / mi (mix of new BD, occupied BDAs, and new BDAs)	30–60 /mi (expect 10 – 50% occupied BDs; BDs and BDAs indistinguishable)

Table 1: Indicators and expected values for each phase. Phase 1 is immediately following first implementation and through 1-2 floods following, phase 2 would begin with second construction of structures through floods 3-4, phase 3 would begin with third construction of structures through floods 5-6.

Inventory of Resources

LTPBR implementation requires recovery potential (area of valley bottom that could be recovered as active floodplain) without considerable risk to existing infrastructure or property, existing woody resources to do construction, a flow regime that will perform the necessary sediment transport, and riparian vegetation that will support beaver dam building activity. Here, we perform an inventory/assessment of the riverscape extent, risks

within and adjacent to the riverscape, and a resource analysis of existing vegetation and flow regime.

Riverscape Extent - Valley Bottom Mapping

The valley bottom of the project area is composed of (1) active channel, (2) active floodplain, (3) inactive floodplain and (4) terraces and fans. Terraces and fans are presumed to be inaccessible by the riverscape and are thus not targets of restoration. There is a large disparity between the surface area of active and inactive floodplain components within the project area (Figure 2), suggesting ample restoration opportunities exist.

Figure 2: Maps of active and inactive floodplain components of the valley bottom of summit creek within the project area. Counterclockwise (starting at top) is moving upstream within the reach.

Identified Risks within & Adjacent to Riverscape

The main hazards adjacent to the riverscape are the Smithfield Canyon Road and the Smithfield Canyon Campground. The road mirrors the stream for the entirety of the project reach, is within the valley bottom and historically active floodplain, and is within 50 ft of the stream channel for the entire project reach. As the road is within the valley bottom and in close proximity to the stream, it effectively reduces the total valley bottom area available to the stream for lateral migration.

Figure 3: Approximate locations of the stream channel (blue), infrastructure hazards (red), and the valley bottom extent (orange). Note that the presence of the road north of the channel essentially acts as a new valley bottom extent for the purposes of maintaining infrastructure, reducing the size of the valley bottom available to the stream for lateral migration.

Risk vs. Opportunity Assessment

As the road poses a risk on the river’s right for the entire length of the channel, the opportunity on the river’s right is limited to small spaces of inactive floodplain or areas where the bank alongside the road is adequately protected from erosion by rocks or well-established vegetation. The opportunities on the river’s left are abundant as there are no risks to infrastructure aside from the campground alongside the lowest ~0.25 miles.

Recovery Potential Space

Synthesis for each project reach of proportion of valley bottom available as/for recovery potential. This should reflect the stakeholder/landowner’s current values.

Resource Analysis

Assessment of Current Conditions and Recovery Potential

		Planning								
What?		Status & Context						What's Possible		
When → Indicators ↓		Existing Conditions			Historic Estimate			Recovery Potential		
Proportion of Active Valley Bottom		15%	±	10%	100%	±	5%	45%	±	10%
Structure Indicators	Jam Density (LWD jams / km)	2	±	1	30	±	10	5	±	2
	Jam Capacity (LWD jams / km)	10	±	5	35	±	10	5	±	2
	Beaver Dam Density (beaver dams / km)	0	±	0	25	±	10	4	±	1
	Beaver Dam Capacity (beaver dams / km)	2	±	2	30	±	15	5	±	2
Complexity Indicators	Number of Active Channels	1	±	1	2	±	2	0	±	0
	Number of Active Channels	0	±	0	0	±	0	0	±	0
	Diffluence Density (# / km)	1	±	1	2	±	2	0	±	0
	Confluence Density (# / km)	1	±	1	3	±	2	0	±	0
	Floodplain Channel Head Density (# / km)	1	±	1	1	±	1	0	±	0
	Pool Density (# / km)	3	±	2	35	±	15	5	±	2
	Mid Channel Bar Density (# / km)	1	±	1	15	±	10	2	±	1
Riffle Density (# / km)	3	±	2	15	±	5	2	±	1	

Table 2: Existing conditions assessed visually during a field visit. Historic Estimate based on models produced by Wheaton et al. available on Riverscapes Data Exchange, and Recovery

Potential represents restoring approximately 15% of the historic capacity of each indicator (except for proportion of active valley bottom) with the Phase 1 implementation.

Geomorphic Condition

Summit Creek presents a significant disparity between its active floodplain area of 4,683 sq meters and inactive floodplain area of 33,316 square meters. Within this context, a low-tech process-based approach to target inactive floodplain areas while preserving the road and campground nestled within the project vicinity is very possible. Many areas can be identified (Figure 2) that are valley bottom wherein the riverscape could be re-introduced while not significantly impacting the road.

Identification of pathways of recovery

Summit Creek is currently in the widening (stage 4) phase, and partial recovery (constraints imposed by existing infrastructure prevent full recovery) of the anastomosing (stage 0) phase is the principal goal of this project (Figure 4). In order to achieve recovery of the stage 0 geomorphic condition, it is required that aggradation and widening occur. LTPBR aims to achieve widening through aggradation and therefore accessing previously inaccessible floodplain areas, and through lateral erosion.

Figure 4: Stream evolution model based off of Cluer and Thorner 2013, adapted by Wheaton et. al., 2015

Flow Regime's ability to "Do the Work" of Restoration

In order for structural additions to the channel to achieve restoration outcomes, geomorphic processes that propagate the forced diversity throughout the channel and floodplain must be present. These geomorphic processes require sufficient river energy (i.e., flow) to move sediments and increase habitat complexity. Summit Creek has a flow regime more than capable of doing the geomorphic work necessary for restoration to be efficacious (Figure 5, 6, 7).

Figure 5: Flow duration curve derived from 19 years of continuous streamflow data. Although old, these metrics still provide a reasonable representation of flows within Summit Creek. Statistic Date Range: 10/1/1961 - 9/30/1979

Figure 6: Condition of Road following the spring 2023 runoff. This diagonal bar formed at an elevation significantly higher than the 2022 channel, suggesting significant sediment transport occurred.

The majority of the floods that do the highest “geomorphic work” within Summit Creek are produced by snowmelt runoff. By Mar 15 we have surpassed the peak median snowpack and are currently at 124% of the median snowpack (for the past 3 decades) (Figure 7), suggesting this year's melt will produce the necessary runoff to induce geomorphic change within our project area.

Figure 7: Snowpack in snow water equivalent for the Bear River Range.

Riparian Condition to support Process of Wood Accumulation

Figure X: A Riparian Condition Assessment map produced using the RCAT tool in Riverscapes Data Exchange developed by the Riverscapes Consortium. The majority of the project reach is classified as moderate riparian condition while the tributaries have good to intact riparian condition. Field visits to the site confirm sufficient vegetation for wood recruitment and vegetation, though the riparian vegetation is dominated by upland woody species.

Project Objectives

(revisit problem and purpose and confirm or clarify and then recast management goals as SMART objectives (see page 8-9 of Chapter 3 (Links to an external site.)) and in terms of measurable objectives and indicators that tie to riverscape health) .

Design - Phase 1

Overall Project Plan

The primary objective of our designed complexes is to reconnect abandoned side channels and reactivate historic floodplain areas. The secondary objective of our designs is to increase hydraulic variability and lateral movement of the channel facilitating greater water distribution and sediment transport dynamics. The utilization of inactive floodplain zones offers an opportunity to not only improve, but also expand the habitat extents, providing refuge and breeding grounds for various aquatic and terrestrial species. Overall, implementation of the designed structures will improve aquatic and riparian habitat, increase biodiversity, and bolster the ecological resilience of Summit Creek, mitigating the impacts of disturbances and promoting long-term sustainability.

Design Objectives

There are 4 main objectives within our design, they are: reconnection with abandoned side channels, reactivation of historic floodplain areas, increase hydraulic variability, and increase lateral extent of the channel. Each of these objectives seeks to progress the Summit Creek riverscape towards a stage 7 (Laterally Active) or Stage 8 (Anastomosing) classification according to the Cluer & Thorne (2013) riverscape evolution model. Achieving these riverscape stages will take multiple stages of restoration. Feasibility of realizing the final goal of stage 0 (Anastomosing Wet Woodland, or Anastomosing Grassed Wetland) is limited by infrastructure within the valley bottom, eg. road and campground.

- Reconnection with Abandoned Side Channels: This objective involves identifying and reactivating side channels that no longer regularly convey water. Reintroducing flow into these channels supports our broader goals of improving and expanding aquatic and

riparian habitat. This objective may be achieved with large complexes in the first stage of implementation, but may take multiple stages to be fully realized.

- Reactivation of Historic Floodplain Areas: This objective focuses on bringing historic floodplain areas back into reach of Summit Creek's typical high flows. Reactivation of historic floodplain areas supports our broader goals of improving and expanding aquatic and riparian habitat. This objective may be partially achieved with large complexes in the first stage of implementation, but may take multiple stages to be fully realized.

- Increase Hydraulic Variability: This objective focuses on the non-uniform, highly variable types of flow forced by implementation of in-stream structures. Examples of various flow types are constriction jets, ponding flow, bank overflow, and riffle-pool sequences, and uniform planar flow. Increasing hydraulic variability supports our broader goals of improving in-stream fish habitat, and dynamic sediment transport processes. This objective can be easily achieved in the first stage of implementation.

- Increase the Lateral Extent of the Channel: This objective focuses not on simply widening the channel, but on widening the area in which water may be distributed at various flows, and increasing the proportion of active valley bottom. Increasing the lateral extent of the channel supports our broader goals of expanding and improving aquatic and riparian habitat, and bolstering the ecosystem resilience of Summit Creek. This objective may be partially achieved with large complexes in the first stage of implementation, but may take multiple stages to be fully realized.

Typical Structure Types

Variation in the exact design of structures is bound to occur during implementation based on constraints set by woody resource availability and specific geomorphic conditions at the structure location. Despite this variability, the general layout and function of structures of a particular type will remain constant, and are subsequently described.

Channel spanning PALS (Post Assisted Log Structures) and BDAs (Beaver Dam Analogs) are implemented to create backwater, to raise the water surface to near or above bankfull and achieve overflow, and/or encourage hyporheic flow/ higher water table within nearby riparian zones nearby.

Mid Channel PALS and Bank Attached PALS (on both sides, open center) are implemented to create a constriction jet on either side or in between the structure(s), and create bar depositing eddy flows directly behind and below the structures (i.e., fish habitat). Bank Attached PALS are used to constrict the channel and create a hydraulic jet with directed flow that may achieve bank erosion, bed scour, etc.. In cases, a bank attached PALS is implemented with the goal of creating a pool built which is sustained by the hydraulic force. Other times the bank attached PALS will be aimed directly at the bank to erode the bank and widen the channel or remove obstacles to floodplain connection, ie: a levee. These structures are included in the design to begin the process of increasing connectivity to floodplain zones, or to simply increase hydraulic variability.

Figure 8: Typical Structures used in design, including bank attached post-assisted log structure/bank blaster (upper left), mid channel post-assisted log structure (upper right), beaver dam analog (bottom left), and channel spanning post-assisted log structure (bottom right).

Individual Complex Designs

Complexes ordered from downstream moving upstream.

Complex 1

Figure 9: Design for complex 1.

Complex Narrative

The overall design of complex 1 aims to reactivate an abandoned side channel (at least in part) on river right. The uppermost structure is a channel spanning PALS that aims to pond flow to at or near bankfull height. This structure will raise the water table on river right, likely re-wetting the abandoned side channel through hyporheic flow. The lower

structures (mid channel PALS) aim to erode banks on either side of the channel and convert these areas to active channels. These structures will achieve some geomorphic work at low flows (e.g., moderate bank erosion and ponding), but the real effects should occur during and following a moderate to high flow event where sediment transport is more likely. This complex aims to achieve full recovery potential after at least 2 typical floods and potentially another implementation phase should structure(s) fail.

Complex 2

Figure 10: Design for complex 2

Complex Narrative

The design of this complex targets low points in the inactive floodplain and utilizes ponding structures and targeted flows to breakdown banks, strategically scour parts of the

bed, and distribute flow over portions of the currently inactive floodplain. In low flows, the zones of influence pictured above most accurately depict the anticipated effects in low flows. Moderate and high flows would come with greater overflow into the adjacent inactive floodplain areas. Much of the work done by these structures is designed to lessen the difference between the average water elevation and the floodplain elevation. Later stages of the design can utilize the hydraulic work done by these structures to better access the inactive floodplains at low flows.

Complex 3

Figure 11: Design for complex 3

Complex Narrative

The overall design of Complex 3 is three channel spanning PALs that are designed to reactivate abandoned side channels and use inactive floodplain on both sides of the river. In low flows, the effects within Complex 3 are anticipated to be minimal, with water levels

likely remaining relatively stable within the main channel and adjacent floodplain areas. The side channels may see limited flow, potentially leading to some water stagnation but offering opportunities for vegetation growth and habitat development. Moderate flows would likely trigger increased activity within the side channels, with water levels rising and potentially spilling over into the inactive floodplain areas. This influx of water could facilitate sediment deposition and nutrient replenishment, supporting the growth of riparian vegetation and enhancing overall habitat diversity. At high flows, the PALs would play a crucial role in directing water into the side channels and floodplain areas, effectively reducing the main channel's hydraulic pressure and mitigating erosion. The increased water volume would foster dynamic interactions between the channels and floodplain, promoting habitat connectivity and facilitating natural processes such as sediment transport and nutrient cycling. Throughout these flow conditions, the zone of influence for Complex 3 would be evident through observable changes in hydrology, geomorphology, and vegetation patterns. Progress towards the complex objectives, such as habitat restoration and floodplain reactivation, would be reflected in the extent and intensity of ponding behind the PALs, the development of diverse riparian vegetation communities, and the establishment of functional ecological connections between the main channel, side channels, and floodplain. Ultimately, achieving full recovery potential would entail sustained monitoring and adaptive management to ensure that the complex continues to support healthy riverine ecosystems and fulfill its ecological objectives over time.

Complex Summary

Complex 3 comprises three-channel spanning PALs aimed at reactivating abandoned side channels and utilizing inactive floodplain areas. Key metrics of use include ponding behind PALs at bankfull flows, increased flow and water movement in side channels, sediment deposition, and nutrient replenishment in floodplain areas. Post-construction, immediate monitoring focuses on water levels and vegetation establishment. After 1-2 typical floods, assessment shifts to sediment deposition rates, flow dynamics, and vegetation resilience.

Following a big flood, evaluation encompasses structure integrity, channel morphology changes, erosion mitigation, and long-term monitoring data analysis.

As-Built: Phase 1

Phase 1 Implementation

Figure 12: As-Built after the April 13 build day for the lower complex.

Figure 13: As-Built after the April 13 build day for the upper complex.

Anticipated Additional Phases

To achieve full recovery, additional implementation phases are deemed necessary, considering site-specific constraints. Phase 2, scheduled for May 4, and Phase 3, slated for June 1, will encompass critical steps in advancing restoration efforts. These phases will entail a comprehensive assessment of the structures implemented during the previous phase, identifying any potential issues or damages and making necessary repairs to ensure the efficacy of the restoration interventions. Additionally, Phase 2 and Phase 3 will focus on expanding restoration efforts by implementing additional structures designed to access new floodplain areas or enhance existing geomorphic variability. This expansion may involve the creation of new complexes or the augmentation of existing ones, with the overarching goal of further improving habitat quality and ecological resilience along Summit Creek.

Adaptive Management Plan

With April 13, marking the successful completion of the first phase of low-tech structure implementation, Summit Creek's restoration is well underway. The adaptive management framework for the Summit Creek restoration project aims to implement iterative management strategies while decreasing risks and increasing understanding of restoration performance. By adopting an adaptive approach, managers learn from implementation, make adjustments based on observed outcomes, and improve the effectiveness of subsequent restoration phases. This will involve evaluation, where regular monitoring of structures and ecological indicators helps to assess their performance, and comparison of observed outcomes with project objectives identify areas for improvement. Additional feedback mechanisms should include engagement with stakeholders, including local communities, government agencies, and scientific experts, to gather feedback on restoration progress. Throughout this process of adaptive management and additional implementation phases, transparent communication of decision rationale and anticipated outcomes to stakeholders is imperative.

Figure 14: From Wheaton et al., 2019: Adapted from Figure 2-2 in NRCS (2007a). Blue arrows represent potentially iterative steps within phases. Solid red arrows represent the traditional linear order of single-phase projects. Dashed red arrows represent the optional adjustments made under adaptive management in response to critical evaluation

References

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